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To cite this article: Bojana Radovanović (2022) Female Imagery in Bogomil Myth, Exegesis and Social Reality: An Overview, Slavonica, 27:1, 1-25, DOI: [10.1080/13617427.2022.2066428](https://doi.org/10.1080/13617427.2022.2066428)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13617427.2022.2066428>

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Published online: 25 Apr 2022.

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Female Imagery in Bogomil Myth, Exegesis and Social Reality: An Overview*

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ABSTRACT

This paper will examine the role of women and, more broadly, the female imagery presented in Bogomil doctrine and practice, as reflected in the Bogomil myth, Biblical exegesis and social reality. The paper explores the relationship between the Bogomil mythological accounts and exegetical practice on the one hand, and the society on the other, in order to clarify whether these Bogomil literary techniques were disconnected from society, or not, and to what extent. Bogomil exegesis mirrored the *underlying situational contexts*, or vice versa. This analysis will also contribute to the wider topic of re-assessing the Bogomil religious identity, as shaped by the elements of the apostolic Christian tradition, but also by extra-canonical and heterodox textual strands.

KEYWORDS

Bogomils; female imagery; exegesis; social practice; apostolic tradition; extra-canonical tradition

This paper will with selected examples from textual sources, shed more light on the Bogomil understanding of the female imagery as portrayed in Bogomil exegetical practice, as well as on the role of women among them, in the domain of social practice. Furthermore, undertaking a quest for the less translucent elements in Bogomil exegesis will help reveal deeper textual and conceptual layers and strands which found their place in the Bogomil worldview, by taking into account the textual material which has not been directly linked to the Bogomils. From these we gain a better understanding of Bogomil religious identity. This material will include the accounts of the Hesychast monastic tradition, as well as sources related to the Gnostic and Early Christian textual heritage.

Finally, this paper will also open the question of the extent to which Bogomil myth and exegesis were connected to, or disconnected from the society.

The role of women among the Bogomils has been investigated by a number of scholars; however, the allegorical resonances of the topic pertaining to female imagery among this group has been only sporadically treated.¹ They yield important insights into female imagery in Late Antique and Early Medieval orthodox and heterodox strands of thinking which also illuminate later heretical movements.²

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*This article originated in the course of the Erwin Schrödinger postdoctoral project funded by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF), under the number J 4431–G, and entitled “*Sicut oves in medio luporum*: religious landscapes, dualist dissent, and the ‘language of heresy’ (11th–13th centuries),” and was presented in a shorter form at the IMC Leeds Medieval Congress in July 2021.

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Bogomil exegesis

Pre-Arrangement of Male and Female souls according to Bogomil cosmological myth

The Bogomils were particularly keen on the allegorical exegesis of the Scriptures and often innovatively embellished Biblical material.³ In Bogomil cosmological myth, conveyed by the *Interrogatio Iohannis*, the female bodies were inhabited by the souls of the first heaven, whereas the male bodies with the souls from the second heaven.⁴ Satan, after he had formed the first human bodies, ordered the angel from the second heaven to enter the body of Adam, and the angel from the first heaven to enter the body of Eve. This implies that the female souls originated from the heaven more distant from God's divine realm of light than that of men.

Cain's sister calomena

Euthymius Zigabenus, monk and Biblical exegete (1050–1120) mentions Cain's sister⁵ in Bogomil mythological elaborations in an account stemming from the twelfth century, which in all likelihood reflects some more ancient Judaic extra-canonical strands, at the set-intersection between the Slavonic and Judaic extra-canonical traditions.⁶

As conveyed by Euthymius,

He (Satan) slipped into the inward parts of the serpent, deceived Eve, slept with her and made her pregnant, so that his seed might get a start on and master the seed of Adam, and as far as possible destroy it and not allow it to increase and grow. Soon she fell into labour and brought forth Cain from her coition with Satanael, and his sister like him, named Calomena. Adam became jealous and also slept with Eve and begot Abel, whom Cain immediately killed, and so brought murder into life. This is why the Apostle John says that 'Cain was the evil one'.⁷

The story of Calomena found its place in the Bogomil version, conveyed by Euthymius Zigabenus, as Stoyanov writes⁸:

In the [...] Bogomil version of the seduction of Eve by the Demiurge she begot twins, Cain and his sister Calomena, from Samael-Satan while Abel was born after her human union with Adam. Cain, the 'seed of Samael', slew Abel, 'the seed of Adam', and brought murder and death into the world. However, after his shape-changing and intercourse with Eve, Samael-Satan lost his creative potency, even his divine form, to become dark and abhorrent.⁹

As suggested by Sanidopoulos, this particular name stems from the 11th/12th c. Jewish source, *The Chronicles of Jerahmeel*,¹⁰ which, in turn, echoes the accounts conveyed by Pseudo-Philo's early history of Biblical events, dated to the first century.¹¹ Furthermore, similar stories of Cain marrying his sister are found in the Clementine Homilies, Book of Adam and Eve, the Cave of the Treasures and other pseudepigraphic books on Adam and Eve of Syrian origin between the fourth and the sixth century'.¹²

Thus, according to the *Chronicles of Jerahmeel*, Adam fathered three sons and three daughters: Cain and his twin, Qalmana, his wife, and Abel and his twin, Deborah his wife.¹³

The Pseudo-Philo's *Biblical Antiquities*, upon which the *Chronicles of Jerahmeel* drew, was compiled from several Hebrew sources, including Hebrew and Aramaic versions of certain deuterocanonical books of the Septuagint.¹⁴ So, according to the ancient

Jewish tradition and legends, Calomena was daughter of Samael and Eve. As demonstrated by Loos, the Jewish origins of the legends of the 'Samael circle' including the story on Calomena, found their echo in Bogomil myths.¹⁵

These topics including the mention of Cain's sister, which were knitted around wider and more comprehensive themes involving the sexual intercourse of Eve with Satanael and the engendering of their progeny, seem to have stemmed out of the Gnostic conceptual realm, but originated in Judaic tradition.¹⁶ The circle of related apocryphal stories are also connected to the tradition of the descendants of Seth, which found their place among the Gnostic cosmological narratives.

The story about Cain's sister appears in the Slavonic, as well as in the Armenian and Hebrew traditions.¹⁷ In the Armenian tradition, the apocryphal and pseudepigraphal texts relating to the corrupt descendants of Cain are also found, among the material pertaining to Adam and Eve.¹⁸

Calomena is also mentioned in the early-eighteenth-century collection of Old Testament pseudepigrapha, as Kalmena.¹⁹ Fabricius, the compiler, postulates that it was through the Pseudo-Methodius' *Apocalypse* that the account of Kalmena has spread wider to the Slavonic populace.²⁰ Cain's sister is mentioned in both volumes of these pseudepigraphic codices. In the first one, the relation to Pseudo-Methodius as a key-link in the transmission chain has been underlined.²¹ In the second volume of the synonymous work, there is also an account of Calemera/Calmana.²²

According to Moses Gaster, the textual tradition of Cain's sister has reached Slavonic *Palaeas*²³ – historiographic compendiums containing canonical and extra-canonical narratives – from the *Book of Jubilees*,²⁴ and consequently, entered the Bogomil teachings, via Pseudo-Methodius. The remaining open questions are when, why and how this tradition reached the Bogomils.²⁵

The *Apocalypse of Pseudo-Methodius*, an apocalyptic world history originated in the seventh century as a Syriac text and falsely attributed to Methodius, the fourth-century bishop of Olympos, may have, judging by the above-mentioned, represented an important link in the transmission chain of the Biblical extra-canonical material to Slavonic populations. Four separate redactions have reached Byzantium at the early stage. In most likelihood, it was translated into the Bulgarian redaction of the Old Church Slavonic in the late ninth-early tenth century, in the workshop of Preslav.²⁶ Could that be the place where the Bogomils have heard of or read about the story of Calomena and inserted it into their exegetical account?

Hence, the information on the spread of the Jewish population in the Byzantine Empire, and in the Balkans is significant in this respect, regarding the possibilities of actual contacts having occurred between Bogomils and Jewish groups. A significant quantity of this information comes from accounts on pilgrimage and travel, and also from the observations of Benjamin of Tudela, a twelfth-century Rabbi and traveler.²⁷ Furthermore, the Jewish population was allowed a certain degree of tolerance during the Palaeologian era (1261–1453), when they were allotted a peaceful co-existence with other foreign nationals and heretics, in the Christian cities, but still without intermingling with the Christian populace.²⁸ As for Bulgaria, the Jews in all likelihood settled there after the ninth century, when Jewish slave-dealers appear on the periphery of the Empire at the close of the reign of Basil I (r.867–886) – in Bulgaria and Venice.²⁹ The question of direct contacts between the Jewish and Bogomil groups needs to be researched more fully, but

it is evident that the mingling of various ethnic populations was taking place in the Byzantine lands, facilitating contact between people, and their symbolic universes.

Theotokos and Theotokoi

Judging from the retelling of Euthymius Zigabenus, the Bogomils used to 'say that those of their faith, in whom dwells what they think of as the Holy Spirit, are all called *Theotokoi*. They too bear the logos of God and bring it to birth by teaching it to others. The first Theotokos had nothing more than themselves'.³⁰ Hence, Bogomils considered themselves the God-bearers, carriers of the Holy Spirit (Logos) which dwelt in them, and presumably believed that they gave birth to it through their teachings. This also points to the importance of the oral tradition in their circles.³¹ Consequently, the Mother of God was in Bogomil exegesis only a symbol of God-bearing and carrying God within – and delivering it to the world through teachings.

This topic so highly laden with symbolic language, found its place in the mystical theological current among the Athonite monks, in the fourteenth century. During the controversy over Hesychasm this terminology came to light. The Hesychast tradition had roots in earlier monastic strands (in the writings of Maximus the Confessor (d. 662) and Gregory of Nyssa (d. ca. 395), among others), and entered the spotlight of public life in Byzantium.³²

The Hesychast controversy emerged around the year 1337, when Barlaam, the Calabrian monk (c. 1290–1348) who was in Constantinople during the reign of Andronicus III Palaeologus (r. 1328–1341) as abbot of Monastery of St. Savior, visited Mount Athos, where he got acquainted with the Hesychast tradition.³³ Barlaam especially examined the writings of Gregory Palamas (c. 1296–1357/9), teacher of Hesychasm, and was scandalised by this technique and ascetic practice. He even held it to be polytheistic, since Palamas postulated the difference between God's uncreated and unseen divine essence, and God's energies/operations, also uncreated, but visible and knowable.³⁴

Nevertheless, the semantic field of 'being pregnant with the Spirit' resonates with earlier, apostolic tradition. Thus, Gregory Palamas quotes Basil the Great (330–379) and says:

For according to St. Basil, 'Spirit-bearing souls (πνευματοφόροι ψυχαί), when illuminated by the Spirit, both become spiritual themselves and shed forth grace upon others. From this comes foreknowledge of things future, understanding of mysteries, apprehension of things hidden, distribution of spiritual gifts, citizenship in heaven, the dance with the angels, unending joy, divine largesse, likeness to God, and the desire of all desires, to become god'.³⁵

Gregory of Sinai (1260s–1346) spoke similarly and employed the analogous typology, portraying those, who had received the divine grace, as being pregnant with the Holy Spirit (... Οἱ τὴν χάριν δεχόμενοι ὡς οἱ ... ἔγκυμωνοῦντες τῷ Πνεύματι ...).³⁶

Nikithas Stithatos, one of the forerunners of Hesychast mystical tradition (born around 1020), disciple and biographer of Symeon the New Theologian (949–1022), analogously compared the soul imbued with divine things with mother of the divine Logos, having become 'conceived' with Logos through repentance.³⁷

As both Golitzin and Gouillard have brought this complex issue to our attention, the Athonite mystical tradition mirrors the earlier theological current attested among the Early Christian theologians.³⁸ Nevertheless, this curious imagery is found in the

Valentinian Gnostic tradition as well. The metaphors of pregnancy and birth pregnancy of the perfect (*teleios*) are found in the Gospel of Philip.³⁹ By all appearances, the semantic undertones exceed the social and religious setting of the Bogomils only, and their origin may well be difficult to decipher, but still, this topic merits to be taken into consideration more in detail and above all else, points to the conceptual diversity having emanated – *nolens, volens* – from the Bogomil exegesis.

Rachel as the heavenly father

The Bogomils substantially enriched their Biblical exegesis with an innovative and creative allegorical methodological approach. For example, they interpreted the passage in the Gospel of Matthew (2:16, 18) in the following way:

Then Herod, when he saw that he had been tricked by the Magi, was in a furious rage, and he sent and killed all the male children who were in Bethlehem ... 'A voice was heard in Ramah, wailing and loud lamentation, Rachel weeping for her children; she refused to be comforted, because they were no more'. (allusion to Jeremiah 31:15)

They tell the story that Rachel was a widow who had two infant daughters (in the original she had sons). When Herod gathered together the male children, she altered them to look like boys (μεταχηματίσαι ταύτας εἰς ἄρρένας, καὶ προσαγαγεῖν ὡς υἱοῦς), thinking that they would deserve honour and favour from him, and brought them forward as sons. When the same thing happened to them as to the other boys, the other mothers simply wept, but Rachel was inconsolable, because in her attempt to outwit Herod she had herself been outwitted and had destroyed her daughters for nothing. Allegorizing the story, they say that Rachel is the heavenly Father and that her children are the soul of Adam and the soul of Christ which were murdered by Herod, that is, the cosmocrator; the Father weeps inconsolably for their loss'.⁴⁰

In the Bogomil interpretation, Rachel had daughters whom she dressed as sons, contrary to the original. That could imply that the soul in Bogomil exegesis epitomized a female principle (daughters), whereas the spirit represented male. In the Old Testament, Rachel was the younger daughter of Laban, sister of Leah and wife of Jacob, mother of Joseph and Benjamin (Gen. 29–31, 33). After a long period of barrenness, and after having acquired children through her servant Bilhah whom Rachel claimed as their own, Rachel eventually bore Joseph, and after some time, Benjamin. Unfortunately, she died in childbirth. Importantly, Joseph and Benjamin would become the forefathers of the two of twelve tribes of Israel. Rachel and her sister Leah are remembered as the two 'who together built up the family of Israel' (Ruth 4:11). More precisely, Rachel has thus become the ancestor of the Northern Kingdom, called Ephraim after Joseph's son. However, after the Assyrians have expelled Ephraim and Benjamin, Rachel came to represent an epitome of the mourning mother, in grief for her lost children (cf. Jer. 31:15).⁴¹

Rachel in Matthew mourns her sons, typifying people of Israel. She was, in the early centuries of the Christian era, brought into connection with the Virgin Mary, thus having become *mater dolorosa*.⁴² Her mourning over children is described by Jeremiah, as inconsolable mother (31:15, retold in Matthew 2:16, 18). This demonstrates the role of allegorical interpretation among the Bogomils, and the 'fluctuation' of the female features in their exegesis.

In trying to analyze the ‘fluctuating’ female motif in Bogomil theology by topos or by analogy, the image of divine androgyny first emerges.⁴³ The underlying theme here may well be that of the re-appropriation of the angelic asexuality and of the angelic state of perpetual virginity, which was rooted in the early Christian tradition.⁴⁴ In the scriptural exegesis of Philo Judaeus (d. c. 50), the male is superior to female because he represented the more rational parts of the souls, while the female represented the less rational; the easiest way for women to approach the male level of rationality was for them to deny their sexuality and remain virgins.⁴⁵ St. Jerome (c. 342/7–420) was of opinion that ‘when the woman wishes to serve Christ more than the world, she will then cease to be a woman and will be called man’.⁴⁶ St. Ambrose (c. 340–397) stressed the spiritual and moral superiority of the female virgins, facilitating them to approach the angelic asexuality and perfection’.⁴⁷

Furthermore, this – but also the representation of souls of Adam and Christ in the Bogomil interpretation of the passage in Matthew – may in fact outline the image of soul as symbolical representation of female, versus that of the spirit as the representation of male, as it is said in the Gospel of Thomas: ‘I will draw her (Mary Magdalene) male so that she also may become a living spirit like you males. For every woman who has become male will enter the Kingdom of Heaven’⁴⁸ (logion 118).

Divine androgyny is also attested in the Gnostic tradition, in the story of Simon Magus’ journey together with Helen, a Tyrean prostitute, who, as Simon was the incarnation of the divine Idea – ἐπίνοια – created by the male Mind (νοῦς). After having absorbed the higher male principle, *epinoia* became the androgynous Mother of all.⁴⁹

The motif of the heavenly Mother is frequently encountered in Gnostic texts and could offer one possible explanation for Rachel’s transvesting daughters.⁵⁰ More precisely, the Holy Spirit represents the First Thought, *Protennoia*, Mother of the living, the androgynous Sophia in the Sethian-Ophite and Barbeloite mythology. In the *Apocryphon of John*, a Sethian Gnostic apocalypse, the First Thought of the Invisible Spirit is the Mother Barbelo, called the Father’s Pronoia, an androgynous Mother-Father, the Womb of the All.⁵¹ Barbelo is also androgynous in Trimorphic *Protennoia*, another Sethian Gnostic treatise.⁵² In the *Gospel of the Egyptians*, she is the male virgin.⁵³

As pointed out by Turner,

It is not Barbelo’s maternal characteristics that are stressed (in the Sethian Platonizing treatises); it is rather her status as the Knowledge or Intellect of the Invisible Spirit that is emphasized, an entity which Platonists traditionally treated in masculine terms as Intellect (nous). She is no longer so much Mother Barbelo as she is the masculine Aeon of Barbelo. The erstwhile Virgin has become male.⁵⁴

Consequently, the motif of androgyny smoothly aligns to that of asexuality and asceticism – whether originated within apostolic, or Gnostic lore – and Bogomil exegetes were not, in all likelihood, unfamiliar with it.⁵⁵

In-Between and beyond: fluidity of gender (re)presentations

The world-view and cosmological beliefs of the Bogomils could be explained through their docetic beliefs, intimately linked with the concept of the aural conception and the underlying role of the Virgin Mary. Consequently, they believed that the Virgin had not really conceived and born Jesus in a natural way, but through her right ear. This resonates

with their docetic beliefs, according to which Jesus had corporeal body only in appearance, in fact he was a spiritual being.⁵⁶

Consequently, for the Bogomils, the Mother of God was not the *Theotokos*; rather, they referred to themselves as *Theotokoi*. They may have received the inspiration for their *Theotokoi* concept from the mystical Athonite tradition, which would have served as a conveyor of a more ancient, early apostolic tradition. Nevertheless, if we make a conjunction with Bogomil views on Rachel, and the ensuing fluidity of gender roles, we may also ascribe the Bogomil exegetical practices and mythological concepts to some Gnostic-leaning tendencies, but also to the early Christian ascetic tradition.⁵⁷

The 'fluidity of gender', in Bogomil exegesis, as discussed above, is to be related to metaphysical sphere and wider encircling asceticism. Asexual virginity was pursued by ascetics and mystics in the early Christianity and Middle Ages and at times women would renounce marriage, and choose an ascetic life-style. The pursuit of spiritual advancement was reachable through renunciation of the world and of her own body. In the Syrian Orient, this impetus led many to embark on endeavors inherent to monastic life, and the postulate of virginity was highly praised by the theologians, as well as by early Christian and Gnostic communities.⁵⁸ This topic also merits to be viewed and more thoroughly researched from a broader perspective encompassing female monastic aspirations in the Early Christianity and in the Byzantine era.⁵⁹

Bogomil practice

Bogomil female members

In the *Alexiad* (Ἀλεξιάς), written around the middle of the twelfth century by Anna Komnene (1083–1153), daughter of the emperor Alexios I Komnenos (r.1081–1118), it is reported that Basil, the Bogomil patriarch, had twelve disciples whom he called 'apostles', and some poor women and disciples of questionable moral and bad character (Βασίλειος ... δώδεκα μὲν ἔχων μαθητάς, οὓς καὶ ἀποστόλους ὠνόμαζε ... γυναῖα κακοήθη καὶ παμπόνηρα).⁶⁰ The process of Basil in Constantinople could be dated to the period between 1097 and 1110.⁶¹ But, according to Obolensky, it is difficult to believe in Anna's claim that Basil was surrounded by women of bad morals.⁶² No other source from that period accuses the Bogomils of sexual immorality. On the contrary, the Bogomils were known for their asceticism.⁶³ At a later date, there was confusion between Bogomils and Messalians, who were frequently accused of immorality⁶⁴ and Anna may have been pre-figuring this, but contemporaries such as Zigabenus made a distinction between the two movements – as demonstrated by Obolensky.⁶⁵ It is still uncertain to what extent Messalians and Bogomils came together or whether the confusion was a wilful misunderstanding of the situation by their opponents at a later date.⁶⁶

After a certain amount of time spent in theoretical education, the true, genuine baptism by Holy Spirit occurred for Bogomil initiates, among which were women also, who were allowed to become perfects themselves. In the late tenth century, Cosmas the Priest (fl. 970s), a medieval priest and theologian renowned for his anti-Bogomil position, composed his *Sermon* in Old Church Slavonic⁶⁷, and stated:

The heretics practice confession to one another and loose sins when they are themselves caught in the toils of the devils. It is not just the men who do this, but the women as well,

which is worthy of condemnation. For the apostle says, 'I permit no woman to teach or have authority over men; she is to keep silent'. (1 Tim. 2:12).⁶⁸

An interesting and significant account comes from Euthymius of Periblepton, describing the Byzantine Bogomil heresy in the eleventh-century. The leader of those Bogomilian branch, John Tzurillas, is mentioned as an 'abbot' who illegally entered the monastery of Acmonia in Phrygia together with his wife, whom he termed as an 'abbess'.⁶⁹

Sometime later, in 1143, the two Cappadocian bishop-monks Leontios of Balbissa and Clement of Sasima who embraced Bogomil ideas, were charged with having women ordained as deaconesses and allowing to them 'to read the holy gospels and to serve mass together with Clement'.⁷⁰ In spite of the fact that no consensus has been reached regarding over whether Leontios and Clement were indeed Bogomil heretics, this episode on the female deaconesses is important as it illustrates the existence of such a practice in twelfth century Byzantium, especially when considered alongside other evidence on female Bogomil members considered above.⁷¹

In the compilation of legal codes, known as the *Nomocanon of St. Sava* and composed in the early thirteenth century, the practice of appointing women as heretical leaders and teachers was attributed to the Bogomils. In spite of the fact that many segments of chapters 61 and 63 on heretics have been taken from earlier documents,⁷² it is significant that these descriptions of Bogomils apparently corresponded to the current situation in Serbia regarding this heresy.⁷³

Comparison across time periods reveals certain topological analogies with preceding heresies. Namely, similar practices of female priesthood had existed previous to the emergence of Bogomilism. Timotheus, the Constantinopolitan presbyter (fl. 600/700) wrote in his *De Marcianistis* that this heresy is known under various appellations: Messalians, Enthusiasts, Euchites, Enthusiasts, among others. In the sect of the Marcionists, which emerged in the second century, women perform functions of *magistrae*, female ministers (*Isti mulieres promovent in suae haeresis magistras*).⁷⁴

It has also been suggested in scholarship, on the Messalian heresy – which had chronologically preceded the Bogomils and which offers some important structural and topological analogies with them – women sometimes took over the role of *magistrae*, as it was the case among the Manichaeans, Marcionites, and Montanists.⁷⁵

The Messalians originated in Mesopotamia, and spread to Syria and Asia Minor in the second half of the fourth century. They often blended into monastic communities and dressed as monks. They were expelled from Syria, but they left their imprint upon some monasteries in Lesser Armenia. The third ecumenical council of Ephesus in 431 accused them and stressed the false conception of asceticism among the Messalians and their propensity towards monasteries. They were numerous in Armenia between sixth and the tenth centuries.⁷⁶ Nevertheless, the Messalians were extinguished around the year 722. However, these complex questions of mutual relations between the heresies preceding the Bogomils cannot be answered with certainty, at least for the time being.⁷⁷

Female followers and supporters of the bogomils

During the Hesychast controversy, Varlaam of Calabria accused the Palamite monks of the Messalian heresy.⁷⁸ Namely, in 1345, Gregory Akyndinos (ca. 1300–1348) wrote on the nun Irene of Thessaloniki (also called Irene Porine), who supported a number of Athonite

monks accused of heresy, and not only: according to Gregory, Irene acted as a minister and leader, having introduced Athonite monks to Bogomilism in the late third decade of the fourteenth century.⁷⁹ She preached and helped disseminate Bogomil teachings into the most powerful Orthodox monastic stronghold. Irene of Thessaloniki was a prominent female leader of the heretical monks in Thessaloniki in fourteenth-century (ca. 1330s), and was in some accounts described as revered as a prophetess.⁸⁰ Another mention left by the renowned erudite Michael Psellos (d. 1078) of a prophetess associated with heresy was that of Dosithea, the prophetess of the island of Chios.⁸¹ The account of Dosithea and two monks accused of heresy in the middle of the eleventh century sheds light on the existence of prophetic practices in the Byzantine realm and the presence of heterogeneous religious tendencies throughout Byzantium. Dosithea was not directly brought into connection with Bogomilism, but rather with Messalianism and Manichaeism, among other – such as pagan prophesying practices, Chaldeism and Neoplatonism, thus revealing an underlying syncretistic *milieu* from which she had apparently emerged; a *milieu* which could have had some common resonances with some traits of the Bogomil doctrine.⁸²

Bearing in mind that Bogomilism shared some doctrinal, organizational and conceptual analogies with Catharism, another dualist movement which undoubtedly marked the High Middle Ages,⁸³ it is worth investigating some interesting parallels which emerge between the functions held by the women in the Bogomil and Cathar ranks. The *perfectae* were active and engaged in social life.⁸⁴ Not only frequently did they offer their monetary support, but also underpinned the Cathar movement in terms of accommodation and provisions. However, the important segment of the Cathar ritual practice, *apparelamentum*, corresponding to the public confession of sin, was performed by men only, and women did not occupy priestly roles. Nevertheless, female members could carry out preaching and office-giving services, but not as deaconesses.⁸⁵ However, only in case of a lack of male *perfecti* could women take up leading functions in the ritual of *consolamentum*. The accounts of those women performing *consolamentum* are very rare: the *consolamentum* was performed by Cathar women in case of need only.⁸⁶ Nonetheless, the performance of pastoral roles by the *perfectae* was well attested.⁸⁷ Consequently, the Cathar female members were allowed to preach and confer the sacrament that they had received.⁸⁸

In the twelfth and thirteenth centuries, the role of women grew increasingly important in orthodox and heretical religious movements in Western Europe. Women were often seen as patrons, participants, or supporters.⁸⁹ In the mid- and late-twelfth century South of France, in the region between Carcassonne, Albi and Toulouse, noble Cathar women and men would often offer support and accommodation to the itinerant preachers of the Languedoc. At the beginning, these women and men helped facilitate the spread of Cathar networks throughout the wider community. Through time, until the dusk of its existence, the Cathar movement reached bourgeois and peasant circles as well, and found supporters there.⁹⁰

The ladies of the region such as Aude and India de Fanjeaux, Raimonde de Durfort, Saure de Mortier, Fays de Lahille would frequently gather together in the house of Guilhabert de Castres, the famous Cathar, senior son (*filius maior*) or spiritual deputy, of the Cathar bishop of Toulouse. Guillelme de Tonneins, one of those ladies, organized her own house as to serve the *perfectae*. Noble women held an important role in the Cathar-

Occitan milieu: elderly ladies, or widows, would dedicate themselves to the service of the Cathar religious houses of the Languedoc, thus providing logistical support for Cathar networks.⁹¹

Blanche of Laurac was also a prominent local noblewoman who was in the service of the Cathars as a *perfecta*. Blanche founded a community of Cathar women in the early thirteenth century, encouraged religious discussion, and organized public debates between Cathars and Catholics led by Diego of Osma at Montreal in 1207, and between the Cathars and Waldensians in 1208. Such women were responsible for passing Cathar doctrines through the generations: Blanche organized a Cathar household with her daughter, the young *perfecta* Mabilia, and raised her grandchildren as Cathars, as did other ladies of the region.⁹²

The practice of noble women serving as patrons to other religious orders – for example, to Dominicans, Waldensians and Humiliati – was not uncommon. In Northern Europe, the female spiritual and pastoral patronage found undoubtedly its apogee in the Beguines and Poor Clares in Italy.⁹³

There are parallels here with early Christianity, in the formative stage of the Christian piety and religiosity, and in that elements of the early Christian tradition have been attested in Bogomil theology.⁹⁴ Jerome of Stridon (d.420) wrote extensively on the female role and on the concept of female asceticism within the Christian communities, which significantly influenced the ensuing phases of Christian asceticism. The so-called ‘Aventine circle’ gathered around Jerome in the fourth-century Rome, consisted of female supporters and devotees who frequently offered monetary support to the saint.⁹⁵ Paula, Marcella, Asella, Blesilla (Paula’s daughter), Eustachium (Paula’s daughter), Lea, and Albina were among its members.⁹⁶ Paula and Marcella held prominent roles and centered this female devotional community around their pursuit of asceticism and dedication to Jerome’s Biblical mentorship – just as the Cathar *Bonnes Femmes* would offer their help and supported the Cathar network and logistics, roughly eight centuries later.⁹⁷ The network of Roman aristocratic women played an important role in the spiritual life of the epoch. The members of the Aventine circle withdrew to suburban retreats, where they engaged in reading and studying Scriptures and charity.⁹⁸ Widows and virgins would often find their place among them, just as was the case in apostolic times. This tradition is comparable to the early Christian female ascetics in the suburbs of Alexandria who had pursued the life of a hermit when widowed.⁹⁹

Both Paula and Marcella were from noble families, born around the middle of the fourth century. Paula’s devotion to Jerome’s spiritual guidance developed especially upon her widowhood, when she took vows of perpetual chastity. Later, Paula used her family resources to maintain the pilgrim hostel, named ‘Mary’s Inn’, established by herself, Jerome, and Fabiola in the Holy Land.¹⁰⁰

In a letter to Pammachius, Jerome spoke of another hospice for strangers which, in conjunction with Fabiola, Pammachius had set up at Portus, and described his own similar institution in Bethlehem. Namely, Jerome provides us here with vivid and colorful information on the duties performed by the women:

I myself was not at Rome but in the desert – would that I had continued there – at the time when your father-in-law Toxotius was still alive and his daughters were still given up to the world. But I have heard that they were too dainty to walk in the muddy streets, that they were

carried about in the arms of eunuchs, that they disliked crossing uneven ground, that they found a silk dress a burthen and felt sunshine too scorching. But now, squalid and sombre in their dress, they are positive heroines in comparison with what they used to be. They trim lamps, light fires, sweep floors, clean vegetables, put heads of cabbage in the pot to boil, lay tables, hand cups, help dishes and run to and fro to wait on others. And yet there is no lack of virgins under the same roof with them. Is it then that they have no servants upon whom they can lay these duties? Surely not. They are unwilling that others should surpass them in physical toil whom they themselves surpass in rigour of mind. I say all this not because I doubt your mental ardour but that I may quicken the pace at which you are running, and in the heat of battle may add warmth to your warmth.¹⁰¹

Portrayal of Bogomil women judging by their exegesis and practice

The Bogomils were against marital sacrament, because in their eyes, this world was the Devil's creation.¹⁰² Nevertheless, this was only valid for the spiritual elite, *perfecti* and *perfectae* who followed precepts of extreme asceticism, and not to those who occupied the ranks of believers.¹⁰³ Analogously, Catharism condemned marriage, along other Catholic sacraments. However, just as was the case among the Bogomils, this strict view was upheld among the perfects only, whereas Cathar believers and supporters were allowed marital union.¹⁰⁴

Consequently, this can be correlated to the practice of monastic vows, with celibacy being one of the main prerequisites – as mentioned above. Analogously, Bogomils described themselves as being 'earthly angels', dedicated to the service of God, and not to procreating.¹⁰⁵ In the aim to corroborate their views, they turned to Matthew 22:30 ('... at the resurrection people will neither marry nor be given in marriage; they will be like the angels in heaven') and the apostle Paul, who did not marry and said 'I wish that all of you were as I am'.¹⁰⁶ The Bogomils of Asia Minor also claimed that 'those, who do not leave their wives, cannot be saved'.¹⁰⁷ Similar opinions were spread among the Italian Cathars.¹⁰⁸ If the candidate for the perfect was a woman, she was supposed to seclude herself from her husband, and vice versa.¹⁰⁹

Hence, for the Bogomils, marriage did not represent an authentic sacrament. Among the Patarens of Bosnia, the only valid marriage was spiritual (*nuptiae spiritualis*), concluded between the husband-Christian, and his wife – the faith (*inter Christianum virum et fidem mulierem*).¹¹⁰ Cosmas the Priest describes Bogomil opposition to marriage.¹¹¹ Similarly, in Cathar communities, carnal marriage was considered a deadly sin (*matrimonium carnale fuit semper mortale peccatum*), and a genuine marriage was represented by a union of soul with God (*bonum matrimonium erat quando anima nostra per bonam voluntatem Deo coniungitur*).¹¹²

Nor were the early Christians unfamiliar with 'spiritual' (celibate) marriages. Among the Gnostics, the Marcionites in Persia and Mesopotamia were celibate, and the followers of Valentinus as well.¹¹³ This resonates with the Gnostic motif of baptismal sacrament and mystical marriage.¹¹⁴ As related above, in the account of Timotheus on the Marcionists in the seventh century, the author also mentioned the belief of that sect that the soul was married to the heavenly bridegroom, *quo mulier in viri concubitu*.¹¹⁵

The motif of a 'bridal chamber' represents the highest of the sacraments in the Valentinian system within the baptismal context – to which only the celibates are accepted – but also appears in other, predominantly Syrian, *milieux*.¹¹⁶ It is also found in Syriac

liturgy, as well as in the writings of Cyril of Jerusalem (c.313–386), Gregory of Nazianzus (329–390), and John Chrysostom (c.347–407).¹¹⁷ This strong and picturesque symbolism most likely derived its inspiration from the Epistle to the Ephesians (5:22–33), and the underlying foundation motif of the church as Christ's bride. Additionally, the Old Testament motif of Israel-Judah as a bride to Yahweh – echoing Yahweh's covenant with Israel-Judah, as described in the prophetic books of Isaiah, Jeremiah, Ezekiel, and Hosea – is significant to mention.¹¹⁸ Importantly, the Valentinian rite encompasses spiritual marriage of the initiate with his angel, epitomized in the marriage of Sophia and the Savior (also mirroring the *topos* of the church as the bride of Christ). In the Valentinian elaboration of this mythological concept, the angels symbolize individual manifestations of the Savior, who has been received by spiritual individuals.¹¹⁹

Bogomil anti-marital views reflected Christian ascetic practice, intrinsically related to monastic circles, but also perhaps to Messalian precedents.¹²⁰ As has already been stressed, some Bogomils had visited Orthodox monasteries, mingled unrecognized among monks, and later publicly propagated their anti-ecclesiastical views against marriage.¹²¹

As demonstrated in the examples of the social engagement of discussed above, there was a role for women-supporters and active participants in religious movements, such as the Bogomils. These women apparently had a logistic and supportive function, apart from their role as disciples. Moreover, as has been argued, female agency often included prophecy in Christian communities,¹²² and represented another facet of female religious identity. Furthermore, this female religiosity was more often expressed in private settings than in the public domain.¹²³ However, it should also be remembered that the correlation between heresy and femaleness in a metaphorical sense occurred in the early Christian authors' attempts to advocate an orthodox faith and suppress heretical expression.¹²⁴ This may lie behind the frequent associations of women with heresy, so neatly shown to be a probable misconception by John Arnold.¹²⁵ Nevertheless, this does not mean that women did not play important, specific and well delineated roles in medieval heresies, Bogomilism included.

Concluding remarks

The female imagery which was conveyed by Bogomil mythology, and reflected in the Bogomil exegetical method, shows an insufficiently explored amalgam of the elements stemming from Early Christian, but also Gnostic-leaning and extra-canonical strata.¹²⁶

Moreover, the creative allegorical interpretation of the Bogomils resulted in the 'fluctuation' of the role of the female element in their exegesis, as shown in this paper. At the same time, women had important roles in social settings. Thus, the female element in their exegesis at times denotes only a symbol – a parallel can be drawn with Andrew Cain's observations on the manner in which Jerome depicted women of the Aventine circle, as symbols of ascetic aspirations¹²⁷ – which is not directly relevant to women in real-life events.¹²⁸ Consequently, Bogomil complex and creative Biblical exegesis, revealing the rich mythological substratum, appears at times rather abstract and not directly connected to social reality. Further research would reveal more on this topic.

Women within Bogomil ranks supported the movement in various ways. As practitioners (*perfectae*), supporters, sympathizers, they were undoubtedly a crucial part of the propagation of Bogomil doctrine.

Conclusively, by placing the Bogomils in the wider European perspective of the epoch, it is important to observe that the role of Bogomil women represents by no means an isolated one, but on the contrary, corresponds to the image of women in medieval West who actively or passively participated in religious movements. As supporters, they encouraged the heterodox tendencies and helped the propagation of informal religious movements.¹²⁹ Nevertheless, as neatly demonstrated by John Arnold, one must beware of jumping to appealing conclusions in making the over-arching and maybe even anachronistic hyperbolized link between women and medieval heresies – since they were, judging by the source material, less numerous and less active than man.¹³⁰ This is highly probable in case of the Bogomils too, but some more research in sociological direction is needed in order to elucidate this question thoroughly. However, it should be said that the women's role were important, albeit maybe distinct from that of men – also given the fact that the expression of female religiosity was tainted with engagement in providing logistic service, but also prophecy, judging by the afore-mentioned examples stemming from the ranks of the earlier heretical movements.

It would be highly productive for the further research to identify the transmission channels by which the Bogomils incorporated the specific extra-canonical elements in their belief system, regarding chronology, origin, and impetus which lay behind this process, as this would greatly enhance our understanding of Bogomil religious identity, which seems to have been shaped by the elements reminiscent of the Early Christian, as well as of some heterodox, extra-canonical and potentially Gnostic strands.

Notes

1. Vasilev, "Bogomils, Cathars, Lollards"; Vasilev, *Heresy*, 43–6; Angelovska-Panova, "Statusot na ženata"; Angelovska-Panova, "The Role of the Woman"; Stoyanov, "The Debate"; Stoyanov, "Esotericism"; Stoyanov, *The Other God*, 275–84; Obolensky, *Bogumili*, 141, 202, and Angelov, *Bogomilstvoto*, 219–21.
2. See Cox Miller, "Women" (and esp. part 1, "Women's Roles in the Church," 15–68, part 2, "Women and Virginity," 69–152, and part 5, "Female Imagery and Theology," 289–322); Müller, "Concepts"; Diem, "The Gender"; Arnold, "Heresy"; Barber, "Women and Catharism"; Biller, "The Common Woman"; Jacobsen Buckley, *Female Fault*; Tokić, "On Women's Element"; Hoffman, in *The Status of Women* on women in Gnostic and Orthodox circles in the first centuries of the Christian era expresses an opposing view to the high opinion on women, as taught by Gnostics, as proposed by Elaine H. Pagels in *The Gnostic Gospels*; McVey, "Gnosticism, Feminism and Elaine Pagels"; King, *Images*, and Cerioni, *Revealing Women*.
3. *Euthymii Zigabeni*, ed. Migne, PG 130: 1321–22; Hamilton, "The Bogomil Commentary"; Obolensky, *Bogumili*, 218–20, and Radovanović, "The Language of Heresy."
4. Note some variants in the apocryphon *Interrogatio Iohannis* (the full name of this apocryphon written before 1190 most likely in Slavonic is *Interrogatio Iohannis apostoli et evangelistae in cena secreta regni coelorum de ordinatione mundi istius et de principe et de Adam*): the male souls inhabited the third heaven, whereas the female ones the second; or, the male souls inhabited the second heaven, and the female ones the first, see Ivanov, *Bogomilski*, 78; Obolensky, *Bogumili*, 210; Angelov, *Bogomilstvoto*, 178; According to the Carcassonne version, Adam's soul originated in the third heaven, whereas that of Eve in the second one, cf. Ivanov, *Bogomilski*, 78.

5. The variants of the name Calomena are: Calmena, Calmana, Calomela, Calemera, Kalmena, Kalomena, Kelemath, and Qalmana.
6. This research segment of a very complex nature merits a more detailed analysis which exceeds the scope of this paper; however, the main lines of research are here presented.
7. Sanidopoulos, ed. *The Rise*, 81.
8. *Ibid.*; cf. Stoyanov, *The Other God*, 266–7.
9. Stoyanov, *The Other God*, 267.
10. Gaster, trans. *The Chronicles of Jerahmeel*. Accessed September 29, 2021. <https://www.sacred-texts.com/bib/coj/coj030.htm>.
11. Cf. Philo of Judaea. *Biblical Antiquities*, ed. James, 1.1.
12. Cf. Sanidopoulos, ed., *The Rise*, 141, note 39.
13. Cf. Gaster, trans., *The Chronicles*, 26.1. Accessed September 29, 2021. <https://www.sacred-texts.com/bib/coj/coj030.htm>; Turner, *Sethian Gnosticism*, 106, esp. note 19.
14. See Ps.-Philo, *Liber antiquitatum biblicarum* 1.1; James, ed., *Philo of Judaea. Biblical Antiquities*.
15. Loos, *Dualist Heresy*, 85–6; Skowronek, “Remarks,” 134.
16. Stroumsa, *Another Seed*, 46; see Turner, *Sethian Gnosticism*, 75, 77, 106, 159, 168; see Orlov, *Selected Studies*.
17. Cf. Stone, *Selected Studies*, 3–54, esp. 42, on the Armenian sources on the history of Cain and Abel.
18. See Stone, “The Reception,” and *Adam and Eve in the Armenian Tradition*, 11–82.
19. Fabricius, ed., *Codex Pseudepigraphus* I, 44, 109, 125.
20. Cf. Loos, “Satan als Erstgeborener Gottes,” 28; Fabricius, *Codex Pseudepigraphus* I, 109; Jagić gives quotations from Slavonic *Palaea* on Eve giving birth to Cain and Calmana: *Slavische Beilage*, 62–3; on Pseudo-Methodius’ transmission in Slavonic milieu, see: Jouravel, “Beobachtungen zu Methodios’ Schrift De Lepra,” 212–13.
21. Cf. Fabricius, ed., *Codex Pseudepigraphus* II, 44, 109, 125.
22. Fabricius, ed., *Codex Pseudepigraphus* II, 44.
23. Cf. Orlov, “The Jewish Pseudepigrapha,” 4.
24. See Albani, Frey and Lange, eds., *Studies*.
25. Gaster, *Ilchester Lectures*, Appendix A, 147–208, pp. 173, 191; cf. Stoyanov, *The Other God*, 267; see also Flusser, “*Palaea Historica*,” and Adler, “Parabiblical Traditions.”
26. Cf. Miltenova, “Historical Apocalypses,” 709–10; Brzozowska, “Who Could ‘the Godless Ishmaelites From the Yatrib Desert be,’” 369–70; Stoyanov, *The Other God*, 158.
27. See Kaufmann, “A Hitherto Unknown Messianic Movement”; Kulik, “Jews and the Language of Eastern Slavs,” 114: on Jewish pilgrims, the messianic movement during the first crusade in 1096, and in general on Jewish population in Constantinople and Thessalonica; Andréadès, “The Jews in the Byzantine Empire” – on Benjamin of Tudela and his trip in the second half of the 12th century to Byzantium: 1–2 testimony on the distribution of the Jews in the Empire and sources attesting the Jewish population in Byzantium; 2–7 – distribution of Jewish communities in Greece and Byzantium; see also Adler, “The Itinerary of Benjamin of Tudela”, and Živković, *Južni Sloveni pod vizantijskom vlašću* [South Slavs under the Byzantine Rule], 53. – on Jews, Armenians and Slavs in Peloponnese and in Greece.
28. See Charanis, “The Jews in the Byzantine Empire”.
29. Cf. Starr, *The Jews in the Byzantine Empire*, 63, 215–17, on the absence of Jews from Bulgarian lands before 800; on the earliest mention of the Jews in Bulgaria, 31, 159, 193–4, 213.
30. “Ἀέγουσι τοὺς τῆς πίστεως αὐτῶν, ὅσοις ἐνοικήσει τὸ παρ’ αὐτοῖς ἅγιον Πνεῦμα, πάντας θεοτόκους καὶ εἶναι, καὶ ὀνομάζεσθαι, βασιτάσαντας καὶ αὐτοὺς τὸν λόγον τοῦ Θεοῦ, καὶ γεννήσαντας αὐτὸν διὰ τοῦ διδάσκειν ἐτέρους, καὶ μηδὲν πλέον αὐτῶν ἔχειν τὴν πρώτην Θεοτόκον”, Cf. Sanidopoulos, ed., *The Rise of Bogomilism*, 109.
31. See Radovanović, “Spreading the Word.”
32. Cf. Hamilton-Hamilton, *Christian Dualist Heresies*, 54–5; Meyendorff, *Byzantine Hesychasm*.
33. See Russell, “The Hesychast Controversy.”
34. Gregory Palamas and his disciples defended the Hesychast doctrine at three different synods in Constantinople in the 1340s. In 1341, a synod was held at Constantinople and condemned

- Barlaam, who then returned to Calabria. Gregory Akindynos (ca. 1300–1348) was originally Palamas' friend, but later became one of his main opponents. The three other synods were held: upon the second, Barlaam's supporters gain a victory, but upon a final Synod in 1351, presided by the new Emperor John VI Cantacuzenus (r. 1347–1354), the Hesychast doctrine was pronounced orthodox. One of the most limpid overview of the Hesychast theology is found in the text by Gregory Palamas, "The Declaration," 418–25. For more information on Hesychasm, see: Strezova, "Byzantine Hesychasm in the 14th and 15th Centuries"; Meyendorff, "Is 'Hesychasm' the Right Word?"; Meyendorff, "Mount Athos" See also Stoyanov, *The Other God*, 228–32, and Rigo, *Monaci esicasti*.
35. Gregory Palamas, "Topic of Natural and Theological Science," 381 (quoting Basil the Great in PG 32:109).
 36. Gregory of Sinai, *Capita de ascesi*, ed. Migne, PG 150: 1244A.
 37. Nikitas Stithatos, "On the Inner Nature" 120–21.
 38. Cf. Golitzin, "Earthly Angels"; Gouillard, "Quatre process," 22–7; Sabo, "The Proto-Hesychasts," 22–67, and 178–210. The more detailed analysis exceeds the scope of this paper.
 39. Cf. Wayne, "The Image of the Androgyne," 190–91; Brown, *The Body and Society*, 116–20.
 40. "Ἀλληγοροῦντες δὲ τὸν λόγον φασί, Ῥαχὴλ μὲν τὸν ἐπουράνιον Πατέρα, τέκνα δὲ αὐτοῦ τὴν τε ψυχὴν τοῦ Ἀδάμ, καὶ τὴν ψυχὴν τοῦ Χριστοῦ, ὧν ἀναιρεθειῶν παρὰ τοῦ Ἡρώδου, δηλονότι τοῦ κοσμοκράτορος, κλαίειν ἀπαράλητα τὸν νατέρα διὰ τὸν τούτον ἀναίρεσιν", Cf. Sanidopoulos, ed., *The Rise of Bogomilism*, 115. This information, conveyed by Euthymius Zigabenus, is most likely related to the 12th-century Constantinopolitan Bogomils.
 41. see "Rachel," in Meyers, Craven, and Kraemer, eds., *Women in Scripture*, 138–40.
 42. Tinkle, *Gender and Power*.
 43. Myths of bisexual progenitor were common in Antiquity, see Wayne, "The Image of the Androgyne," 185, note 87; see also Stoyanov, *The Other God*, 270.
 44. See: Cooper, "The Bride of Christ"; Diem, "The Gender of the Religious"; Müller, "Askese und Ekstase"; Müller, "Concepts of Female Leadership".
 45. *Philo Judaeus, Questions and Answers on Genesis*, trans. Marcus, I, 22.
 46. Jerome, *Commentarius in Epistolam ad Ephasios*, ed. Migne, PL 26: 567.
 47. Cf. Ambrose's works on virgins, in *Ambrose: Selected Works and Letters*, ed. Uyl, 371–4.
 48. Doresse, *The Secret Books of the Egyptian Gnostics*, 370.
 49. Cf. Anson, "Female Transvestite in Early Monasticism," 8; cf. Turner, *Sethian Gnosticism and the Platonic Tradition*, 210–12; the "masculinization of the Mother": 754–6, and Sophia as androgynous figure in Sethian Gnosticism; Barbelo-*Pronoia* as Mother-Father in the longer version of the Apocryphon of John, 211; cf. Meeks, "The Image of the Androgyne"; Quispel, "De vrouw in de Gnosis"; see also Diem, "The Gender "; Müller, "Askese und Ekstase," and Cox Miller, "Women in Early Christianity" (and esp. part 2, "Women and Virginity," 69–152).
 50. Turner, "The Virgin that Became Male."
 51. See Layton and Brakke, eds., "The Secret Book According to John."
 52. See Layton and Brakke, eds., "First Thought in Three Forms."
 53. See Layton and Brakke, eds., "The Holy Book of the Great Invisible Spirit."
 54. Turner, "The Virgin that Became Male," 324.
 55. See also: Wiesner-Hanks, "Women, Gender, and Church History"; Bullough, "Transvestites in the Middle Ages"; Anson, "The Female Transvestite in Early Monasticism"; Patlagean, "L'histoire de la femme déguisée en moine"; Lehtipuu, "No Male and Female"; Halsall, "Women's Bodies, Men's Souls".
 56. Cf. Sanidopoulos, ed., *The Rise of Bogomilism*, 87; Hamilton and Hamilton, *Christian Dualist Heresies*, 186; see Radovanović, "Spreading the Word"; Papisov, *Christen oder Ketzer – Die Bogomilen*, 223; Runciman, *The Medieval Manichee*, 60–61, and Hamilton, "The Virgin Mary in Cathar Thought," 26–7.
 57. Still, the direct Gnostic influences should, at least at this point, remain typological and conjectural only, cf. Stoyanov, *The Other God*, 280–81.
 58. on Jerome's views on ascetic life, moral purity, virginity, but also of that inspirational thread in his life and works, see Cain, "The Embattled Ascetic Sage", in his *The Letters of Jerome*, 129–67;

- on Syrian Encratite and Thomasine communities, see Wayne, "The Image of the Androgyne," 193–7, and Brown, *The Body and Society*, 91–2, 116–20.
59. For more information on this issue, see: Talbot, "Women's Space"; Talbot, "Women"; Talbot, "Women and Mount Athos"; Schroeder, "Women in Anchoritic and Semi-Anchoritic Monasticism in Egypt"; Karras, "Female Deacons in the Byzantine Church"; Mitsiou, "Female Monastic Communities."
 60. *Alexiade, Anne Comnène*, ed. Bernard Leib, Book XV, ch. 8, p. 486, l. 54–7; *Alexiadis libri XV*, I, ed. J. Schopen, XV, 8, 351–2; see *Anna Comnena*, trans. Elizabeth A. S. Dawes, 292; Obolensky, *Bogumili*, 202.
 61. Cf. Roach, *The Devil's World*, xv, 63; Stoyanov, *The Other God*, 178.
 62. Obolensky, *Bogumili*, 202.
 63. *Ibid.*, 203.
 64. Cf. *Ibid.*, 60, 193.
 65. Cf. *Ibid.*, 203, note 4.
 66. Cf. *Ibid.*, 251: Obolensky supports the opinion according to which the equalization between the Bogomils and the Messalians took place in the 14th century. However, Puech is of different opinion, in Puech, and Vaillant, *Le traité contre les Bogomiles*, 292–303, as are Hamilton-Hamilton, *Christian Dualist Heresies*, 30, arguing that no direct contact between the Messalians and the Bogomils was attested, since Messalianism has, judging by the evidence at our disposition, not survived beyond the seventh century, contra Sanidopoulos, ed., *The Rise of Bogomilism*, 14–17.
 67. The *Sermon* originated after the death of Tsar Peter (927–969), but before the tsars of Preslav disappeared from the historical stage, cf. Hamilton-Hamilton, *Christian Dualist Heresies*, 27, 114–15; Loos, *Dualist Heresy*, 50, and the earliest manuscript comes from the fifteenth century.
 68. See Hamilton and Hamilton, *Christian Dualist Heresies*, 132 (translated by Yuri Stoyanov).
 69. Cf. Ficker, *Die Phundagiagiten*, 66; Obolensky, *Bogumili*, 178–182; Loos, *Dualist Heresy*, 67–77; Hamilton-Hamilton, *Dualist Christian Heresies*, 33.
 70. Cf. Trizio, "Trials of Philosophers and Theologians," 470; Strezova, "Byzantine Hesychasm," 28.
 71. Gouillard found no direct associations between Leontios and Clement to the Bogomil heresy, cf. Gouillard, "Quatre process," 39–43, 68–81, contrary to Vasilev, "Bogomils, Cathars, Lollards," 327–35; Trizio, "Trials of Philosophers and Theologians," 470; Hamilton and Hamilton, *Christian Dualist Heresies*, 215–19, and Obolensky, *Bogumili*, 222.
 72. On the similarities with the account by Timotheus, Constantinopolitan presbyter, see below.
 73. Cf. Petrović, *Pomen Bogumila – Babuna*, 19–20.
 74. *Timothei presbyteri*, ed. Migne, PG 86: 46–7; the other appellations are: *Marcionistae, Messaliani, Euchitae, Enthusiastae, Choreutae, Lampetiani, Adelphiani et Eustathiani*, cf. *Timothei presbyteri*, ed. Migne, PG 86: 46.
 75. Cf. *Timothei presbyteri*, ed. Migne, PG 86: 52. For more information on the Montanist female preachers, see Benko, *The Virgin Goddess*, 137–50; Shepard Kraemer, *Her Share*, 160–61; Shepard Kraemer, eds., *Women's Religions*, 263–6; on the regulations for Deaconesses, see Shepard Kraemer, eds., *Women's Religions*, 277–8.
 76. For the role of Armenia in the history of heretical movements, see Gero, "With Walter Bauer"; Runciman, *The Medieval Manichee*, 27, 60.
 77. See Stoyanov, *The Other God*, 161–6.
 78. Cf. Strezova, "Byzantine Hesychasm in the 14th and 15th Centuries"; Meyendorff, "Is 'Hesychasm' the Right Word?", and Meyendorff, "Mount Athos."
 79. Cf. Zlatarski, ed., *Žitiето na sv. Teodosija [Vita Theodosii]*, 19; Hamilton-Hamilton, *Christian Dualist Heresies*, 52–3; Constantinides Hero, ed. and trans., *Letters of Gregory*, letter 52, 223–5; Russel, *Gregory Palamas*, 97. According to the majority of the sources, Irene was indeed a leader of Athonite heresy: cf. Rigo, *Monaci esicasti*, 182–3, n. 92; Wolski, "Autoproscoptae, Bogomils and Messalians," 237–8.
 80. Rigo, *Monaci esicasti*, 151, 156–7, 182–3, 233; Obolensky, *Bogumili*, 254–5; Vasilev, "Bogomils, Cathars, Lollards," 327; Hamilton and Hamilton, *Christian Dualist Heresies*, 53, and Meyendorff, "Mount Athos."

81. Cf. Bréhier, "Un discours inédit de Psellos," 383–9, 397–9.
82. Cf. Stoyanov, "Esotericism and Visionary Mysticism"; Eleuteri-Rigo, *Eretici, dissidenti, Musulmani ed Ebrei a Bisanzio*, 146–7, 150–51; Hamilton-Hamilton, *Christian Dualist Heresies*, 123.
83. Cf. Hamilton, "Cathar Links"; Biller, "Goodbye to Catharism?," 284, 288–91, as well as the contributions of Claire Taylor, Robert I. Moore, and John Arnold in Sennis, ed., *Cathars in Question*.
84. See Arnold, "Women and Gender" for important theoretical overview of the relationship between women and heresy.
85. Brenon, *Les Femmes Cathares*, 90–91, 213.
86. Cf. *Ibid.*, 185.
87. *Ibid.*
88. *Ibid.*, 210–15; Barber, "Women and Catharism"; see also Müller, "Frauen," and Müller, "Katharinnen im Rheinland."
89. Roach, *The Devil's World*, 115, 182–92.
90. Brenon, *Les Archipels Cathares*, 324–40; Abels and Harrison, "The Participation."
91. Cf. Abels and Harrison, "The Participation."
92. Brenon, *Les Archipels Cathares*, 325–6; see Biller, "The Common Woman."
93. Cf. Diana d'Andolo, Clare of Montefalco, see Roach, *The Devil's World*, 187–90; Biller, "The preaching," 133–7.
94. See Hamilton-Hamilton, *Christian Dualist Heresies*, 30, 116–17, 130, and Radovanović, "Spreading the Word."
95. Cain and Lössl, *Jerome of Stridon*, 42.
96. On the "Aventine circle," see Cain and Lössl, eds., *Jerome of Stridon*, 52, notes 40, 56.
97. Cain and Lössl, "Rethinking Jerome's," in Cain and Lössl, eds., *Jerome of Stridon*, 47–57; Duval, "Sur trois lettres"; Lamprecht, "Jerome's Letter 108 to Eustochium"; Cain, "Jerome's Epitaphium Paulae"; Cooper, "The Bride of Christ"; for lives of Paula and Marcella, the leaders of the "Aventine circle", see Shephard Kraemer, ed., *Women's Religions*, 177–204, and 212–20; on Aristocratic women in Jerome's Roman network, see epistles 23, 24, 48.
98. See Cain, "Jerome's Epistula 117 on the Subintroductae"; Clark, "John Chrysostom," 182.
99. Cf. Bonner, "The Trial of Saint Eugenia," 253; see Cooper, "The Bride of Christ"
100. Cf. Cain and Lössl, *Jerome of Stridon*, 173 (Epp. 66:14).
101. Cf. Jerome's Letter 66, on Eustochium and Paula. Accessed September 29, 2021. <https://web.archive.org/web/20090605153018/http://www.ccel.org/ccel/schaff/npnf206.v.LXVI.html>.
102. Angelov, *Bogomilstvoto*, 219–20.
103. Sanidopoulos, ed., *The Rise of Bogomilism*, 124–5; Obolensky, *Bogumili*, 216.
104. Brenon, *Les Archipels Cathares*, 327, 336.
105. Cf. Cyril from *Vita Theodosii*, Zlatarski, ed., *Žitieto*, 20.
106. 1 Cor. 7:7, New International Version.
107. Ficker, *Die Phundagiagiten*, 66–7.
108. Bonacursus, *Manifestatio*, ed. Migne, PL 204: 781AC; see also Myers, "Morality among Cathar Perfects and Believers," 27–43.
109. Ficker, *Die Phundagiagiten*, 13–14.
110. Cf. Angelov, *Bolomilstvoto*, 221.
111. Hamilton and Hamilton, *Christian Dualist Heresies*, 128; Obolensky, *Bogumili*, 216; *Euthymii Zigabeni*, ed. Migne, PG 130: 1325C.
112. See Douvernoy, *Le Registre d'Inquisition*, 411.
113. For a more expansive view on the topic, including the phenomenon of the *virgines subintroductae*, see Cain, "Jerome's Epistula 117 on the Subintroductae"; Clark, "John Chrysostom," 182; also Clark, "Asceticism in"; Clark, "The Celibate Bridegroom"; Wright Knust, "Seminal Vice"; Brown, *The Making*, 6–88.
114. Cf. Gospel of Philip: Strathearn, "The Valentinian Bridal Chamber in the Gospel of Philip": "The Valentinian Bridal Chamber in the Gospel of Philip" by Gaye Strathearn (byu.edu). Accessed September 29, 2021. <https://scholarsarchive.byu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1013&context=sba>
115. Timotheus, *De Marcionistis*, ed. Migne, 86: 46–7.

116. Cf. Brown, *The Body and Society*, 91–2, 116–20, 167; Wayne, “The Image,” 190–91, 193–7.
117. See Murray, “The Church, Bride and Mother.”
118. Cf. Painter, *The Bridegroom’s Perilous Bride*, 131–3, 141; Villeneuve, *Nuptial Symbolism*, 4–22 (on the prophets), 109–265 (on the New Testament imagery), and 213–46 (on the Ephesians); see Lee, “The Church as the Bride of Christ.”
119. Thomassen, *The Spiritual Seed*, 405.
120. Cf. Obolensky, *Bogumili*, 121–2.
121. Cyril Bosota publicly spoke against marriage and on the desired separation between wives and husbands: Rigo, *Monaci esicasti*, 125, 176, 178, 212; cf. Zlatarski, ed., *Žitiето*, 20.
122. Cf. Brown, *The Body*, 65–7; for the overview of such a complex topic, see: Grabbe, “Her Outdoors’: An Anthropological Perspective on Female Prophets and Prophecy”; Marjanen, “Female Prophets among Montanists”; Nissinen, “Gender and Prophetic,” and Nissinen, “Prophecy and Gender.” Accessed January 18, 2022. <https://oxford.universitypressscholarship.com/view/10.1093/oso/9780198808558.001.0001/oso-9780198808558-chapter-8?print=pdf>.
123. Cf. Clark, “Women, Gender, and the Study of Christian History,” 402, 411.
124. Cf. Burrus, “The Heretical Woman as Symbol.”
125. Cf. Arnold, “Heresy,” 499–501; Clark, “Holy Women, Holy Words.”
126. See also: Radovanović, “From ‘Coats of Skin’ to the ‘Robe of Glory’”, and “The ‘Language of Heresy’”.
127. Cf. Cain and Lössl, “Rethinking Jerome’s” 57.
128. Cf. Clark, “Holy Women, Holy Words,” 429–30.
129. Cf. Roach, *The Devil’s World*, 192.
130. Cf. Arnold, “Heresy and Gender,” 499–501.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

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Abbreviations

PG *Patrologiae Cursus Completus, Series Graeca*. Ed. Jacques-Paul Migne (Paris: Imprimerie Catholique, 1857–1866).

PL *Patrologiae Cursus Completus, Series Latina*, ed. Jacques-Paul Migne (Paris: Imprimerie Catholique, 1841–1855).

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